

Dyslipidaemia among First Degree Relatives of Patients with Graves' Disease – A Cross-Sectional Study from North-Western Nigerian

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Graves' disease is named after Robert J. Graves, who noted an association between exophthalmos, goitre and palpitations in 1835.¹ Graves' disease is an organ specific autoimmune thyroid disorder characterised by hyperthyroidism, various degrees of diffuse goitre, ophthalmopathy, and less commonly pretibial myxoedema.¹ The disease can occur at any age with peak incidence in 20-40year age group.⁴

Data on dyslipidaemia among first degree relatives of patients with Graves' disease from developing countries are limited. There are few published studies on the subject in Nigeria.

Objective: We determined the pattern of dyslipidaemia among first degree relatives of patients with Graves' disease at Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital (AKTH), Kano.

Methods: We conducted a descriptive cross-sectional study at the Endocrinology clinic of AKTH Kano involving 87 first degree relatives of patients with Graves' disease and 87 controls. A pretested questionnaire was filled for each participant after due explanation. Clinical parameters were documented. Blood samples were tested for TSH, fT₃, fT₄, anti-TPO, anti-Tg and lipid profile.

Results: The mean age of the study subjects and controls was 29.38±8.95 years and 31.63±8.81 years respectively with p-value of 0.096. Forty five (51.7%) were males and forty two (48.3%) were females among the study subjects and controls respectively. Elevated total and LDL cholesterol, low HDL cholesterol was found in participants with thyroid dysfunction.

Conclusion: Dyslipidaemia predominantly elevated total cholesterol and LDL cholesterol was found among first degree relatives of patients with Graves' disease at AKTH Kano, Nigeria.

KEYWORDS: Dyslipidaemia, Graves' disease, First degree relatives, Thyroid dysfunction.

INTRODUCTION

Graves' disease is named after Robert J. Graves, who noted an association between exophthalmos, goitre and palpitations in 1835.¹ Graves' disease is an organ specific autoimmune thyroid disorder characterised by hyperthyroidism, various degrees of diffuse goitre, ophthalmopathy, and less commonly pretibial myxoedema.¹ Thyroid Stimulating Immunoglobulins (TSI) bind and activate thyrotropin receptors causing the thyroid gland to grow and the follicles to increase synthesis of thyroid hormones.²

Graves' disease represents 60-80% of all cases of Thyrotoxicosis in different region of the world. The disease occurs in up to 2% of women. Females are involved five to ten times more commonly than males.^{2, 3} The disease can occur at any age with peak incidence in 20-40year age group.⁴ It also occurs in the elderly. The disease has no racial predilection.^{2, 3} The prevalence of GD in Nigeria is about 4.0%.⁵

Graves's disease (GD) is currently viewed as an autoimmune disease of unknown cause. It has strong familial predisposition as 15% of patients have a close relative with same disorder and about 50% of relatives of patients with Graves' disease have circulating thyroid autoantibodies.⁶ Thyroid hormones significantly has effect on synthesis, mobilization and metabolism of lipids.⁷ In general, overt and subclinical hypothyroidism is associated with hypercholesterolemia which is mainly due to elevation of low density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol levels, whereas high density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol concentration is usually normal or even elevated.⁷ In hypothyroid patients, despite the reduced activity of HMG CoA reductase, there is often an increase in the serum total

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cholesterol concentration, mainly due to raised levels of serum LDL cholesterol and intermediate density lipoprotein (IDL) cholesterol.^{7,8} Decreased thyroid secretion greatly increases the plasma concentration of cholesterol because of decreased rate of cholesterol secretion in the bile and consequent diminished loss in the faeces due to decreased number of low density lipoprotein receptors on liver cells.^{7,21} Decreased activity of LDL receptors resulting in decreased receptor-mediated catabolism of LDL and IDL is the main cause of the hypercholesterolemia observed in hypothyroidism.⁷ Hypertriglyceridemia in hypothyroidism is due to decreased activity of lipoprotein lipase (LPL), which results in decreased clearance of triglyceride-rich lipoproteins.^{6,7} Hypothyroid patients usually exhibit elevated levels of high density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol mainly due to increased concentration of HDL2 particles. Decreased activity of the CETP results in reduced transfer of cholesteryl esters from HDL to VLDL, thus increasing HDL cholesterol levels.⁸ It may be concluded that hypothyroidism constitutes a significant cause of secondary dyslipidaemia, a well-known risk factor for cardiovascular diseases.⁹

A significant proportion of first degree relatives of patients with AITD have been found to exhibit overt (6%) and subclinical (22%) hypothyroidism, respectively.¹⁰ Data on dyslipidaemia among first degree relatives of patients with Graves' disease from developing countries are limited. To the best of our knowledge, there are few published studies on the subject in Nigeria.

The present study was conducted with the aim of obtaining data on dyslipidaemia among first degree relatives of patients with Graves' disease at the Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital, Nigeria. This study has filled the gap in knowledge of the subject in Kano northern Nigeria.

METHODS

Ethical clearance with approval number NHREC/21/08/2008/AKTH/EC/2689 and AKTH/MAC/SUB/12A/P-3/VI/2789 was obtained from the ethical committee of AKTH, Kano before commencement of the study. The provision of HELSINKI declaration was respected. Participants were adequately informed about the study clearly in the language they understood, before obtaining written consent. All data collected from the participants was kept confidential.

The study was hospital based, descriptive cross-sectional among first degree relatives of patients with Graves' disease at AKTH Kano. The study participants were first degree relatives of patients with Graves' disease attending the Endocrinology clinics of AKTH Kano. The control participants were age and sex matched apparently healthy hospital staff who do not have first degree relatives with any known history of Graves' disease/thyroid disorder. The study participants were recruited from the Endocrinology clinic of the hospital. The EDM unit runs clinics twice per week (Thursdays and Fridays).

The minimum sample size was determined using the Fisher's formula for cross-sectional studies comparing two proportions.¹¹ A total of 88 study subjects and 88 control subjects (in a ratio 1:1) were recruited for this study.

Participants who met the inclusion criteria were verified and recruited consecutively by convenient sampling. Every consecutive subject who fulfils the inclusion criteria for the study was recruited until completion of the estimated sample size.

A written consent was obtained from the first degree relatives of the patients who consented to participate. A questionnaire with seven (7) sections was administered by the researcher. Details of demographic characteristics obtained from the study subjects and controls were entered into the questionnaire. Five (5) millilitres of blood was collected from each subject in the morning after overnight fast, into a gel activated bottle with aid of vacutainer needle from antecubital vein while adhering to standard protocols by the researcher and research assistant. The collected sample was analysed for TSH, fT₃, fT₄, Anti-Tg, Anti-TPO antibodies and lipid profile.

The data generated was collated, checked, and analysed using a computer based statistical programme for social sciences (SPSS) version 20.0 [SPSS Inc.]. A confidence interval of 95% was used, and a p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

A total of 176 participants who met the inclusion criteria were recruited, this is made up of 88 study subjects and 88 study controls. Two participants (one each from the study subjects and control subjects) did not complete the study. Both declined to report back for blood sample collection. All the remaining 174 study participants completed the study

Socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants

The mean age of the study subjects and controls was 29.38 ± 8.95 years and 31.63 ± 8.81 years respectively with p-value of 0.096. Forty five (51.7%) were males and forty two (48.3%) were females among the FDRs and controls respectively. The predominant age group was 18 -24 and 25 -34 years constituting 37.9% and 36.8% respectively. The least was 45 -50 years contributing 10.3% of the participants.

Clinical characteristics of the study participants

The clinical characteristics of the study participants are summarised in Table 1. The mean age of the FDRs (Group 1) was comparable to that of the study controls (Group 2), 29.38 ± 8.95 years vs. 31.63 ± 8.81 years, $p = 0.096$. However, the mean BMI, heart rate, SBP and DBP differs between the groups with p value of 0.006, 0.022, 0.047 and 0.001 respectively.

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Table 1: Clinical Characteristics of the study participants.

Clinical characteristics (Mean value)	Group 1	Group 2	P-value
Age (years)	29.38 ±8.95	31.63 ±8.81	0.096
Heart rate (bpm)	86.0± 9.7	82.0± 10.3	0.022*
SBP (mmHg)	114.0 ± 11.3	110.0 ± 9.8	0.047*
DBP (mmHg)	74.7 ± 8.4	70.6 ± 8.4	0.001*
Weight (Kg)	63.93±11.45	60.89±9.60	0.059
Height (m)	1.66±0.07	1.67±0.07	0.419
BMI (kg/m ²)	23.2 ± 3.97	21.8 ± 2.97	0.006*

Group 1= first degree relatives of patients with Graves' disease; Group 2 =study control SBP - systolic blood pressure; DBP- diastolic blood pressure; BMI- body mass index.

Laboratory characteristics of the study participants

The laboratory characteristics of the study participants are shown in Table 2. All the parameters analysed were comparable between the two groups, except for total cholesterol and LDL cholesterol which showed significant difference with p-value of 0.0001 and 0.0001 respectively.

Table 2: Laboratory parameters of the study participants.

Parameters (Mean values)	GROUP 1	GROUP 2	p- value
FPG (mmol/l)	4.97 ± 0.88	4.83 ± 0.53	0.207
Total cholesterol (mg/dl)	224.95 ± 48.86	190.36± 33.23	<0.0001*
HDL (mg/dl)	40.33± 15.69	40.66 ± 11.29	0.877
Triglycerides(mg/dl)	107.43 ± 52.49	97.57 ± 43.89	0.181
LDL (mg/dl)	163.91 ± 44.66	130.72 ± 32.02	<0.0001*
TSH (miu/ml)	3.52 ± 4.22	2.50 ± 0.92	0.030*
fT3 (pmol/l)	±1.00	4.31 ±1.009	<0.0001*
fT4 (pmol/l)	16.52 ± 6.33	16.18 ± 4.03	0.671

Group 1= first degree relatives of patients with Graves' disease; Group 2 =study controls ; FPG – fasting plasma glucose; HDL – high density lipoprotein; LDL – low density lipoprotein; TSH –thyroid stimulating hormone; fT4 – free thyroxine; fT3 – free triiodothyronine.

DISCUSSION

In this study, 174 participants comprising 87 first degree relatives of patients with Graves' disease and 87 controls were studied. The study participants were subjected to both physical and laboratory evaluation to determine the pattern of dyslipidaemia among the FDRs compared to apparently healthy controls. In this study, the mean age of the study subjects and the controls, was comparable to the findings of Dayal et al¹⁰ in their study of thyroid dysfunction among first degree relatives of patients with autoimmune thyroid disease. Strieder et al¹¹ however, reported a higher mean age among their study participants compared with the present study. In the index study, the mean BMI of the study subjects and the controls did not differ significantly. Likewise, the heart rate, systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure were comparable between the two groups. The participants were age and sex matched, therefore no. of statistically significant difference in terms of age and gender in this study.

The mean fasting plasma glucose level in this study was comparable between the two groups, 4.97mmol/l and 4.83mmol/l for group 1 and 2 respectively. The HDL cholesterol of the FDRs and controls were also comparable with HDL of 40.33 mg/dl and 40.66mg/dl respectively. However among FDRs with thyroid dysfunction, 10.3% had elevated total cholesterol, 8.1% and 10.3% had low HDL-c and raised level of LDL-c respectively. The finding was similar to that, reported by Santos et al¹³ among euthyroid and hypothyroid individuals. A study by Dada et al¹⁵ from south western Nigeria reported high prevalence of dyslipidaemia (68.18%) in patient with thyroid dysfunction.¹⁵ The difference was due to the study population(existing thyroid dysfunction vs euthyroid FDR). Likewise, Wanjia et al¹⁶ reported association between TSH level and total cholesterol and triglycerides among euthyroid subjects. Another study from Kashmir, India among patients with subclinical and overt hypothyroidism by Mushtaq et el⁷ showed positive association between dyslipidaemia and hypothyroidism. Dyslipidaemia is due to decreased lipolysis and reduced LDL receptor numbers leading decreased LDL clearance and consequent increase in serum lipid levels.^{6, 17}

Elevated total cholesterol, low HDL and raised LDL cholesterol was observed in 19.5%, 6.9% and 14.9% respectively among the FDRs with anti-Tg positivity. While, study subjects with anti-TPO positivity had elevated total cholesterol, raised LDL cholesterol and elevated triglycerides in 5.0%, 2.4% and 5.3% respectively. The pattern of Dyslipidaemia in this study was comparable with previous studies^{18, 19}. Topaloglu et al¹⁸ as well as Kang et al¹⁹ reported positive correlation between TPO-ab positivity with T-c and

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LDL-c and negative correlation between TPO-ab positivity and HDL-c. It has been shown, that as TSH increased, the lipid profile became less favourable, even within the normal range.²⁰

CONCLUSION

Dyslipidaemia predominantly elevated total cholesterol and LDL cholesterol was found among first degree relatives of patients with Graves' disease at Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital, Kano, Nigeria. Dyslipidaemia is associated with thyroid disorders and is paramount all patients with thyroid disorder screened for dyslipidaemia.

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